

ONLINE CYBERBULLYING DETECTION USING NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING

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Abstract—Bullying is defined as targeting an individual or a group of individuals and exposing them to ridicule and negative actions, both physical and mental, deliberately. With the advent of technology, a form of bullying known as cyberbullying has spread very quickly, targeting masses of innocent people very easily. In this project, we focus on applying natural language processing and machine learning techniques proposed to detect and prevent cyberbullying. Before the advent of information and communication technologies (ICT), social interactions occurred within small cultural boundaries, such as geographic locations. Recent developments in communication technologies have significantly transcended the temporal and spatial limitations of traditional communication. These social technologies have created a revolution in user-generated content, online social networks, and rich data on human behavior. This project highlights a new way to demonstrate aggressive behavior on SM websites. We comprehensively review cyberbullying prediction models and identify the main issues in their construction in SM. This project provides insights into the overall process for cyberbullying detection and, most importantly, an overview of the methodology. Though data collection and feature engineering processes have been elaborated, most emphasis is on feature selection algorithms and Support Vector Machine (SVM) models for predicting cyberbullying categories.

Keywords: *bullying, cyberbullying, technologies, social media*

I. INTRODUCTION

There is a lot of history and background on cyberbullying since it has been around for a very long time. Cyberbullying takes place when people use technology to harm others. The terms cyberbullying and cyberbully are attributed to Canadian educator Bill Belsey, founder and president of Bullying.org Canada Incorporated, and leader of anti-bullying efforts [1]. Cyberbullying has been affecting people for a very long time and can hurt people from young teens to adults. Methods of cyberbullying can include threats, sexual harassment, spreading lies, impersonation to post materials to damage a reputation, destroy relationships, or cause other trouble; making someone the subject of ridicule or scorn in discussion forums, chat rooms, or websites; the posting of compromising photos taken without the victim's knowledge or permission, or the editing of photos to embarrass or impugn, such as pasting the victim's face on a nude body; and developing a person's confidence to trick him or her into divulging secrets or embarrassing information. All of these methods are examples of what is currently taking place in today's society.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENTS

Cyberbullying, as the name implies, is the use of cyberspace as a mechanism to bully others, known or unknown to the

bully. Cyberbullying has caused significant issues for those involved, ranging from extreme displays of anger to suicide attempts. This project seeks to explore the different levels of cyberbullying and their sentiment. For a better understanding of the hateful and offensive behavior of a human. While traditional face-to-face bullying has been going on since the beginning of time, cyberbullying is a relatively new form of bullying that has not been taken seriously until recent years. It used to be thought that since cyberbullying does not inflict physical damage on the victim, it is not much of a concern. What these old beliefs were missing was knowledge about what cyberbullying is and how this bullying can cause such an effect on one's psychological state. But today, cyberbullying is one of the biggest issues, and many people don't know how to deal with it or get affected by it. Cyberbullying has caused significant issues for those involved, ranging from extreme displays of anger to suicide attempts. Cyberbullying has a huge impact on our lives, so we need to stop it before people get badly affected by it. That's why this project seeks to explore the different levels of cyberbullying and their sentiment. For a better understanding of the hateful and offensive behavior of a human. The statement of the problem is that cyberbullying has had a huge impact on our lives, and we need to stop it before it overwhelms our society. Cyberbullying is at an all-time high, and bullies are now threatening and hacking people anonymously. Cyberbullying is a big issue, and many people don't know how to face it in our society. Cyberbullying has impacted the lives of many people through the use of social networking sites. So, in total, cyberbullying is a growing thing, and if we don't stop it, future generations can be affected.

III. SCOPE OF PROJECT

Cyberbullying is the use of electronic communication to bully a person by sending harmful messages using social media and instant messaging through digital messages. Cyberbullying can be very damaging to people, especially adolescents and teens. It can lead to anxiety, depression, and even suicide. Also, once things are circulated on the Internet, they may never disappear, resurfacing at later times to renew the pain of cyberbullying. Cyberbullying can be very damaging to adolescents and teens. It can lead to anxiety, depression, and even suicide. Also, once things are circulated on the Internet, they may never disappear, resurfacing at later times to renew the pain of cyberbullying. To overcome these issues, detecting cyberbullying is very important nowadays, which will help to stop cyberbullying on social media networks. In this Cyberbullying Detection System, we have to clarify

the scope to accomplish this project efficiently. Since this is a text-based cyberbullying system, we need to choose the type of text or language to be captured so the system can process it. In this system, we focus only on English-language text. Thus, other language texts will not be captured in this system. Here, among various types of cyberbullying, we are only dealing with harassment, and among harassment, we categorize the cyberbullying world into three types: hate, offensive, and non-hate and non-offensive. This project will raise awareness regarding social media cyberbullying. It will also detect different categories of cyberbullying on a user-friendly website. The government and organizations can easily detect cyberbullying. So, this model for detecting hatefulness and offensiveness in a sentence can be useful for systems that address cyberbullying. This model can also be useful for organizations involved in adult and children's affairs, such as educational institutions, and for people wanting to explore human behavior through text analysis.

IV. OBJECTIVES

The main objectives of this project are as follows:

- 1) To develop a system for detecting cyberbullying using natural language processing techniques.
- 2) To understand human behavior in social media through text sentiment analysis.

V. LITERATURE REVIEW

Computers and other electronics are becoming more a part of our everyday world each day. New technologies are being discovered, and new programs are being made to improve different aspects of our environment. One big example is the use of technology to improve our communication with each other. With the internet, we can email, blog, instant message, create websites, and talk in chat rooms, among other things. The internet is not the only developed mode of communication. Cell phones are becoming more popular than ever. People can use cell phones not only to talk to other people, but also to text, send pictures, and access the internet. Most of these advances have been positive, creating easier ways for people to communicate; however, technology has also had negative effects, especially on youth. School-aged children have started to use this technology to bully others, leading to the rise of cyberbullying [3].

Cyberbullying is best defined by Keith and Martin (2005) as:

“Cyberbullying involves the use of information and communication technologies such as email, cell phone, pager, text messages, instant messages (IM), defamatory personal websites, and defamatory online personal polling websites, to support deliberate, repeated, and hostile behavior by an individual or group, that is intended to harm others” (p.224)[4].

Over 80 percent of teens use a cell phone regularly, making it the most popular form of technology and a common medium

for cyberbullying. About half of young people have experienced some form of cyberbullying, and 10 to 20 percent experience it regularly. Hurtful comments and spreading rumors are the most common types of cyberbullying. Girls are at least as likely as boys to be cyberbullies or their victims, and boys are more likely to be threatened by cyberbullies than girls. Cyberbullying affects all races, and victims are more likely to have low self-esteem and to consider suicide [2,3]. Direct cyberbullying involves repeatedly sending offensive messages. More indirect forms of cyberbullying include disseminating denigrating materials, sensitive personal information, or impersonating someone to cause harm. In this system, we detect whether the text entered by the user on the website falls into the cyberbullying category by categorizing texts as offensive, hate, or non-offensive/non-hate, and provide users with tips to prevent, avoid, and control cyberbullying, harassment, etc.

A student is being bullied when he or she is repeatedly and over time exposed to negative actions by one or more students. The person who intentionally inflicts or attempts to inflict injury or discomfort on another person is engaging in negative actions. Cyber harassment is a form of bullying that occurs in cyberspace. These preliminary studies suggest that cyber harassment is becoming a significant problem. Attempts to reduce this behavior are complicated as “cyber-bullies” may be anonymous, making it difficult for school administrators and parents to identify them. Anonymous communication prevents the detection of harmful behavior, may encourage users to engage in risky behaviors, and may also avert their embarrassment and responsibility [6]. Hate content in social media is ever-increasing. While platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and Google have attempted to take several steps to tackle hateful content, they have mostly been unsuccessful. Counterspeech is seen as an effective way to tackle online hate without harming freedom of speech. Thus, an alternative strategy for these platforms could be to promote counterspeech as a defense against hate content [7].

A. Related Works

Many approaches propose systems to automatically detect cyberbullying with high accuracy.

- 1) Nadine and S [8, 9] proposed a model using the Naïve Bayes machine learning approach, achieving 91% accuracy with a dataset from MySpace.com. Later, they proposed another model using the Naïve Bayes classifier and genetic operations (FuzGen), achieving 87% accuracy.
- 2) Romsaiyud et al. [10] enhanced the Naïve Bayes classifier by extracting words and examining loaded pattern clustering, achieving 95.79% accuracy on datasets from Slashdot, Kongregate, and MySpace. However, the clustering process cannot run in parallel.
- 3) Dinakar et al. [11] aimed to detect explicit bullying language related to (1) Sexuality, (2) Race & Culture, and (3) Intelligence. They used a dataset of YouTube comments and applied SVM and Naïve Bayes classifiers, with SVM achieving 66% accuracy and Naïve Bayes achieving 63%.

- 4) Di Capua et al. [12] adopted an unsupervised approach for cyberbullying detection, using different classifiers inconsistently over their dataset. They applied SVM to FormSpring (67% recall), GHSOM to YouTube (60% precision, 69% accuracy, 94% recall), and Naïve Bayes to Twitter (67% accuracy).
- 5) Haidar et al. [13] proposed a model to detect cyberbullying in the Arabic language, using Naïve Bayes (90.85% precision) and SVM (94.1% precision). However, they faced a high rate of false positives.
- 6) Dadvar et al. [14, 15, 16] constructed a Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier using WEKA, with a dataset from MySpace. They achieved 43% precision and 16% recall, and later applied gender information, achieving 78% precision and 55% recall. In their third paper, they applied Multi-Criteria Evaluation Systems (MCES), Naïve Bayes, decision trees, and SVM classifiers to a YouTube dataset, with MCES achieving 72% accuracy and Naïve Bayes achieving 66%.
- 7) Potha et al. [17] used the SVM approach, achieving 49.8% accuracy. Chavan et al. [18] applied logistic regression and SVM, achieving 77.65% accuracy, 58% recall, and 70% precision on a Kaggle dataset.

The approach in this project involves processing data using natural language processing, followed by applying a Support Vector Machine (SVM) model. The project consists of three main steps: preprocessing, feature extraction, and classification. The preprocessing step involves cleaning the data by removing noise and unnecessary text, followed by tokenization, stop-word removal, TF-IDF feature extraction, and, finally, classification with accuracy, precision, and F1-score evaluation.

VI. REQUIREMENT ANALYSIS

A. Functional Requirements

- Users should be able to enter a sentence and receive a fairly accurate analysis of the entered text.
- Users must receive only one category among the three categories: 'Hate Speech,' 'Offensive Speech,' or 'No Hate or Offensive.'
- Users should be able to view tips for protection from cyberbullying.

Hardware Requirements:

- **Processor:** Intel Pentium 4 or higher
- **Memory:** 1 GB (recommended)
- **Storage Devices:** 10 GB or above

Software Requirements:

- **Operating System:** Windows
- **Browser:** Windows Explorer/Edge/Chrome

B. Non-Functional Requirements

Non-functional requirements, such as performance, cost, interfaces, lifecycle requirements, and efficiency, are essential for successful project completion. The non-functional requirements of the project are as follows:

- The system ensures a good user environment, is user-friendly in operation and provides useful information to the user.
- The system performs efficiently in terms of throughput and response time.
- The system should achieve greater accuracy in analyzing and predicting datasets.

VII. FEASIBILITY REPORT

A. Economic Feasibility

Economic analysis is the most frequently used technique for evaluating the effectiveness of the proposed system. We have conducted economic feasibility studies to determine the operational and maintenance costs. The project requires a mid-range laptop or Android device to run the application, making it economically feasible since the user doesn't need any additional equipment or installation.

B. Technical Feasibility

Technical feasibility concerns the specification of equipment and software that will successfully satisfy user requirements. The team has the necessary hardware, including a mid-range laptop, to develop this project. Additionally, we will deploy it to a hosting provider to ensure the project meets the technical feasibility criteria.

C. Operational Feasibility

Operational feasibility primarily concerns human, organizational, and political factors. It refers to an evaluation that analyzes how well a system operates. The project requires a laptop or Android device to run the application.

VIII. METHODOLOGY

A. Software Development Approach

1) *Iterative Model:* For project development, we have chosen to follow the Iterative Model. With this model, we can start with some of the software specifications and develop the first version of the software. After the first version, if the software needs to be changed, a new version is created with a new iteration. Every release of the Iterative Model ends at a fixed, exact period called an iteration.

The Iterative Model provides access to earlier phases, where variations are made accordingly. The final output of the project is renewed at the end of the Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) process. The Iterative Model is a particular implementation of a software development life cycle (SDLC) that focuses on an initial, simplified implementation that progressively gains complexity and a broader feature set until the final system is complete. When discussing the iterative method, the concept of incremental development is often used liberally and interchangeably to describe the incremental changes made during each iteration. The basic idea behind this method is to develop a system through repeated cycles (iterative) and in smaller portions at a time (incremental), allowing software developers to leverage what was learned from earlier parts or versions of the system.

Fig. 1: Iterative Model

B. Roadmap

A survey shows that 53% of enterprises using AI and machine learning today recognize unexpected outcomes and predictions as the greatest risk when building and deploying machine learning (ML) models [8].

1) *Identifying Problems and Project Needs:* Understanding the project's needs, availability, and data nature is crucial. Every data science project should be 'project first,' with project problems and objectives defined from the outset.

a) *Situational Analysis:* In situational analysis, we should be able to assess current operational performance and identify challenges, bottlenecks, priorities, and opportunities. In this project, the objective, motivation, future opportunities, and uses have been defined.

b) *Defining Ultimate Goals:* Undertake a rigorous analysis of how our project goals align with the modeling approach, identify performance and technology gaps, and define the next steps.

2) *Data Acquisition and Exploratory Data Analysis:* The preceding stages were intended to help the team members define the criteria for project success. After completing these steps, the team was able to prepare for data selection and preparation. The better the data, the better the model. An initial analysis of data should provide guiding insights that will help set the tone for modeling and further analysis. Based on the project needs, we understood how much data is needed to build and train the model.

a) *Red Flags in Data:* Here are some 'red flags' to watch out for in the data:

- Missing variables that cannot be normalized to a unique basis.
- Irrelevant data to the subject of the algorithm. It might be useful, but not in this instance.

Upon encountering any of these red flags, the data may need to be cleaned before implementing an ML algorithm.

Fig. 2: Roadmap for Building Cyberbullying Detection Systems

3) *Data Preparation and Preprocessing:* Once we had a clear understanding of our project goals, the data needed, and had acquired the data, we moved on to the data preprocessing step. The main purpose of data preprocessing in our project is to convert categorical strings into normalized, scaled numerical values. Additionally, processing the dataset's sentences using NLP ensures we have clear, understandable text.

4) *Modeling:* The modeling stage begins with choosing the specific modeling technique to use. At this stage, we generate several models, set them up, build them, and make them ready for training. For this project, we have used the Support Vector Machine (SVM) ML models. Before model creation, the testing method should be developed to review quality and validity. We separated the datasets into training and validation (test) sets. For this project, we used 70% of the data for training and the remaining 30% for test validation. We built the model using the training set and made a quality assessment based on the separate test set.

5) *Model Evaluation:* After evaluating the modeling application's success, we collaborated with domain experts to review the results in a business context. For this project, we referred to several articles that have been deeply and

thoroughly studied and written by domain experts.

This step includes the following parameters:

- **Cross-validation** — dividing data into two or three parts; the first is used for model training, the second for approach selection, and the third, the test set, for final model performance measurement.
- **Confusion Matrix** — a table that compares each class’s number of predictions to its number of instances. It helps define the model’s accuracy, true positives, false positives, sensitivity, and specificity.

For evaluating these techniques, we used Accuracy, F1 Score, Recall, Precision, and a Confusion Matrix.

a) *Accuracy*: Accuracy of a classifier is defined as the percentage of the dataset correctly classified by the method.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{Number of correct predictions}}{\text{Total number of predictions made}}$$

b) *F1 Score*: F1 Score is the Harmonic Mean between precision and recall. The range for F1 Score is [0, 1]. It shows how precise the classifier is (how many instances it classifies correctly) and how robust it is (by not missing a significant number of instances). The higher the F1 Score, the better the model’s performance.

$$\text{F1 Score} = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

c) *Recall*: Recall is the number of correct positive results divided by the number of all relevant samples (all samples that should have been identified as positive).

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{True Positive (TP)}}{\text{Total Actual Positive}}$$

d) *Precision*: Precision is the number of correct positive results divided by the number of positive results predicted by the classifier.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True Positive (TP)}}{\text{Total Predicted Positive}}$$

6) *Deployment: Real-World Integration*: After the model passed validation, we deployed it using the Streamlit framework, which makes it easy to turn data scripts into a web app. The main advantage of Streamlit is that it allows us to run the project and generate output in real time. This will be very helpful if we want to integrate this project into a larger real-time project in the future.

7) *Data Model Monitoring and Maintenance*: No project ends with the deployment stage; the maintenance step comes next. Data changes daily, so a monitoring system is needed to track the model’s performance over time. The main purpose of maintenance is to ensure the system’s full functionality and optimal performance throughout its working life.

IX. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

A. Data Collection

The input dataset was already categorized into different topics of bullying content: (i) Hate, (ii) Offensive, and (iii) No hate and offensive. To perform our experiment, we collected data from comments, text, and chats on social media.

Fig. 3: System Architecture

B. Data Pre-Processing

1) *Tokenization*: Tokenization is a process that splits an input sequence into tokens, where each token is a useful unit for semantic processing. A token may be a word, part of a word, or just a character-like punctuation mark. It is one of the most foundational NLP tasks and a difficult one because every language has its own grammatical constructs, which are often hard to formalize as rules.

2) *Stop Word Removal*: Stop words are words that are so common in language that removing them doesn’t affect the overall message enough to lose meaning. The stop-word list includes terms such as articles, prepositions, conjunctions, and certain high-frequency words (such as some verbs and adverbs). These words are not very meaningful for detecting cyberbullying, so they are removed from texts or comments. Sometimes, the extremely common words, which would appear to be of very little value in helping select documents matching user needs, are excluded from the vocabulary entirely. These words are called stop words, and the technique is called stop word removal.

3) *Stemming*: Stemming is the process of removing and replacing suffixes to reach the root of a word. Stemming programs are commonly called stemming algorithms or stemmers. A stemming algorithm reduces the words “wolf” and “wolves” to the root word “wolf” and “chocolates,” “chocolatey,” and “choco” to the root word “chocolate.” Stemming is an important part of the pipelining process in Natural Language Processing. The input to the stemmer is tokenized words.

4) *Lemmatization*: Lemmatization is the process of grouping together the different inflected forms of a word so they can be analyzed as a single item. Lemmatization is similar to stemming but it brings context to words. So, it links words

with similar meanings to one word. Lemmatization is preferred over stemming because it performs morphological analysis of the words.

C. Feature Extraction

For this project, we need a feature-extraction technique to convert text into a feature matrix (or vector). We used the TF-IDF Vectorizer to extract text. This model involves receiving a list of labeled text, counting words in each collection, and determining how frequently each word appears for each label.

TF-IDF stands for term frequency-inverse document frequency. It highlights specific issues that may not be particularly frequent in our corpus but are of great importance. It is composed of two sub-parts:

a) *Term Frequency (TF)*: Term Frequency (TF) gives us the frequency of the word in each document in the corpus. It is the ratio of the number of times the word appears in a document compared to the total number of words in that document. It increases as the number of occurrences of that word within the document increases. Each document has its own TF.

$$tf_{i,j} = \frac{n_{i,j}}{\sum_k n_{i,j}} \quad (1)$$

b) *Inverse Document Frequency (IDF)*: Inverse Document Frequency (IDF) is used to calculate the weight of rare words across the corpus. Words that occur rarely in the corpus have high IDF scores. It is given by the equation below.

$$idf(w) = \log\left(\frac{N}{df_i}\right) \quad (2)$$

Combining these two, we obtain the TF-IDF score (w) for a word in a document in the corpus. It is the product of TF and IDF:

$$w_{i,j} = tf_{i,j} \times \log\left(\frac{N}{df_i}\right) \quad (3)$$

where:

- $tf_{i,j}$ is the number of occurrences of i in j
- df_i is the number of documents containing i
- N is the total number of documents

D. Training and Testing Data

In supervised learning, the dataset is split into training and testing sets. For this project, 70% of the data is used for training and 30% for testing. As this work employs supervised machine learning techniques, the dataset is split into training and test sets.

In machine learning, the model is created to predict on the test data. The training data is used to fit the model, and the testing data is used to test it. The models generated are used to predict results that are unknown, which are called the test set. The training dataset is used to train the models, which learn the inherent relationships between the input features and the labeled dataset. On the other hand, the testing dataset is completely unknown to the model. Before implementing the

training process, specific features are extracted from the entire dataset to improve accuracy when predicting on the test set.

E. Model Selection

1) *Support Vector Machine (SVM)*: Support Vector Machines (SVMs) are a set of supervised learning methods used for classification, regression, and detection. Although they can be used for regression problems, they are best suited for classification. The objective of the SVM algorithm is to find a hyperplane in an N-dimensional space that distinctly separates the points into classes.

Support Vector Machines are based on the concept of decision planes that define decision boundaries. A decision plane separates a set of objects having different class memberships. The standard SVM takes a set of input data and predicts, for each input, which of two possible classes it belongs to, making the SVM a non-probabilistic binary linear classifier. A Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a discriminative classifier formally defined by a separating hyperplane. In other words, given labeled training data (supervised learning), the algorithm outputs an optimal hyperplane that categorizes new examples.

In two-dimensional space, this hyperplane is a line that divides the plane into two parts, with each class on either side. Intuitively, a good separation is achieved by the hyperplane that has the largest distance to the nearest training data points of any class (so-called functional margin), since in general, the larger the margin, the lower the generalization error of the classifier. SVMs are supervised binary classifiers that are very effective when there are many features. The goal of SVM is to separate a subset of the training data from the rest, called the support vectors (the boundary of the separating hyperplane). The decision function of the SVM model that predicts the class of test data is based on support vectors and uses a kernel trick.

Fig. 4: Iterative Model

Here, the weight vector (w) has to be normal to the hyperplane; b is the bias. The points nearest to the separating hyperplane are called Support Vectors. The support vectors

denoted as x determine the hyperplane position. The distance between the two lines, which are parallel to the hyperplane and have no interior points, is known as the margin. The points that lie on the boundary of the slab and are nearest to the hyperplane are called support vectors (SVM).

2) *Random Forest*: Random Forest (RF) is used to construct cyberbullying prediction models because it combines decision trees and ensemble learning. RF fits several classification trees into a dataset and aggregates their predictions. The construction of RF involves the following steps:

- 1) **Training Data and Attributes**: Set the number of examples (cases) in the training data to N and the number of attributes in the classifier to M .
- 2) **Tree Creation**: Create multiple random decision trees by selecting attributes randomly. For each tree, a training set is chosen by sampling n times from the N instances. The remaining instances are used to estimate the tree's error by forecasting their classes.
- 3) **Node Decisions**: For each node in the trees, randomly select m attributes to base the decision. The best split is computed using these m attributes. Each tree is built fully without pruning.
- 4) **Aggregation**: After creating a large number of trees, each tree votes for the most popular class. The class with the most votes is selected as the output.

RF constructs a model comprising multiple tree-structured classifiers. Each tree contributes to the final decision by voting for the most popular class, and the majority vote determines the output.

3) *Random Forest*: Random Forest (RF) combines decision trees with ensemble learning, aggregating predictions from multiple trees. The construction involves training multiple trees with random attribute selections and aggregating their votes for classification.

F. System Design

1) *Use Case Diagram*: The Use Case Diagram illustrates the interactions between users and the system, showing the various use cases and actors involved.

Fig. 5: Use Case Diagram

2) *Activity Diagram*: The Activity Diagram represents the system's workflow, detailing the sequence of activities and their interactions.

Fig. 6: Activity Diagram

3) *Sequence Diagram*: A Sequence Diagram depicts the sequence of interactions between system objects or components over time.

Fig. 7: Sequence Diagram

Fig. 10: ER Diagram

4) *DFD Level 0*: The Data Flow Diagram (DFD) Level 0 provides a high-level overview of the system, illustrating the major processes and data flows.

Fig. 8: DFD Level 0

5) *DFD Level 1*: The Data Flow Diagram (DFD) Level 1 provides a more detailed view of the system, breaking down the major processes into sub-processes and showing their interactions.

Fig. 9: DFD Level 1

6) *ER Diagram*: The Entity-Relationship (ER) Diagram illustrates the entities within the system and their relationships.

X. TOOLS AND TECHNOLOGY

A. Python

Python is an interpreted high-level general-purpose programming language. Python's design philosophy emphasizes code readability with its notable use of significant indentation. Its language constructs and object-oriented approach aim to help programmers write clear, logical code for both small- and large-scale projects.

B. NumPy

NumPy is the fundamental package for scientific computing in Python. It is a Python library that provides a multi-dimensional array object, various derived objects (such as masked arrays and matrices), and an assortment of routines for fast operations on arrays, including mathematical, logical, shape manipulation, sorting, selecting, I/O, discrete Fourier transforms, basic linear algebra, basic statistical operations, random simulation, and much more.

C. Pandas

Pandas is a software library written for the Python programming language for data manipulation and analysis. In particular, it offers data structures and operations for manipulating numerical tables and time series. The name is derived from the term "panel data," an econometrics term for data sets that include observations over multiple periods for the same individuals. Its name is a play on the phrase "Python data analysis" itself.

D. Matplotlib

Matplotlib is a data visualization library used for 2D plotting to produce publication-quality images and figures in a variety of formats. The library helps to generate histograms, plots, error charts, scatter plots, and bar charts with just a few lines of code. It provides a MATLAB-like interface and is exceptionally user-friendly.

E. SciPy

The SciPy library offers modules for linear algebra, image optimization, integration, interpolation, special functions, Fast Fourier transform, signal and image processing, Ordinary Differential Equation (ODE) solving, and other computational tasks in science and analytics. SciPy depends on NumPy for the array manipulation subroutines. The SciPy library was built to work with NumPy arrays along with providing user-friendly and efficient numerical functions.

F. Scikit-learn

Scikit-learn provides a wide range of supervised and unsupervised learning algorithms that use a consistent Python interface. The library can also be used for data mining and data analysis. The main machine-learning functions that the Scikit-learn library can handle are classification, regression, clustering, dimensionality reduction, model selection, and pre-processing.

G. Deployment Framework

1) *Streamlit*: Streamlit is an open-source Python app framework. It helps us create beautiful web apps for data science and machine learning quickly. It is compatible with major Python libraries, including scikit-learn, NumPy, Pandas, and Matplotlib.

XI. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

A. Data and Methods

The dataset for this final project was sourced from a study called *Automated Hate Speech Detection and the Problem of Offensive Language* conducted by Thomas Davidson and a team at Cornell University in 2017 [21]. The dataset is provided as a .csv file containing 24,802 Twitter text posts, of which 6% were labeled as hate speech.

Since content moderation is so subjective, the labels in this dataset were determined through crowdsourcing and by majority rule. The “class” column labels each tweet as 0 for hate speech, 1 for offensive language, or 2 for neither. To create a different project and adapt the data to my specific business context, we have treated the data as a binary classification problem. Therefore, the final model will predict whether a tweet is hate speech. If it is hate speech or offensive language, it will be classified as a cyberbullied comment; if it is neither, it will be classified as a non-cyberbullied comment.

The conclusions from the research dataset are shown in the figure below.

Fig. 11: True versus Predicted from the original dataset

For figure 7.1.1 above, 40% of hate speech is misclassified: the precision and recall scores for the hated class are 0.44 and 0.61, respectively. Most misclassifications occur in the upper triangle of this matrix, suggesting that the model is biased towards classifying tweets as less hateful or offensive than human coders. Far fewer tweets are classified as more offensive or hateful than their true category; approximately 5% of offensive and 2% of innocuous tweets have been erroneously classified as hate speech. To explore why these tweets have been misclassified, we now examine the tweets and their predicted classes [21]. The conclusion from this dataset is that most tweets have been misclassified, and there is a difference between human coding and the dataset’s predicted results. We have addressed the above-mentioned drawbacks and have also explored the dataset in greater depth to achieve consistent results.[31]

B. Data Columns

Column Name	Description
count	Number of CrowdFlower users who coded each tweet (minimum is 3, sometimes more users coded a tweet when judgments were determined to be unreliable by CF)
hate_speech_votes	Number of CF users who judged the tweet to be hate speech
offensive_language	Number of CF users who judged the tweet to be offensive language or neither
class	Class label for the majority of CF user votes: 1 - hate speech, 0 - not hate speech
tweet	Text containing , #, !, HTTP, etc.
clean_tweet	Tweets filtered through NLP data cleaning process

TABLE I: Testing for Support Vector Machine

C. Visualization and Analysis

Comparison of Unique Words in Each Corpus Label

Fig. 12: Unique Word Using Venn Diagram

Fig. 13: Bigram Visualization

Fig. 14: Average Polarity Scores

Fig. 15: Network of Co-Occurring Words in Entire Corpus of Tweets

count	hate_speech	offensive_language	neither	class	tweet
0	3	0	0	3	2 !!! RT @mayasolovely: As a woman you shouldn't...
1	3	0	3	0	1 !!!!! RT @mleew17: boy dats cold...tyga divn ba...
2	3	0	3	0	1 !!!!!!! RT @UrKindOfBrand Dawg!!!! RT @80sbaby...
3	3	0	2	1	1 !!!!!!! RT @C_G_Anderson: @viva_based she lo...
4	6	0	6	0	1 !!!!!!!!!!!!! RT @ShenikaRoberts: The shit you...

Fig. 16: Top 5 columns in the dataset

The original dataset consists of 25,296 rows and 7 columns. The sentence in the original dataset consists of stopwords (a, an, the, etc.) and symbols (@, #, *, etc.).

⌚ the cell below takes about 3 minutes 30 seconds to run

```
%%time
# training accuracy
base_SVM_accuracy_cv = cross_val_score(SVM_baseline, t
base_SVM_mean_cv = round(base_SVM_accuracy_cv.mean(),

Wall time: 3min 24s
```

Fig. 17: Training time using SVM

Training the dataset took 4 minutes.

	accuracy	precision	recall	f1_score	weighted_f1
Baseline Random Forest	0.878413	0.859128	0.878413	0.862116	0.862116
Baseline Naive Bayes	0.839408	0.816456	0.839408	0.816809	0.816809
Baseline SVM	0.884062	0.894757	0.884062	0.887975	0.887975

Fig. 18: Accuracy Comparison

In Figure 18, the accuracy of SVM is higher compared to the other two algorithms

```
# cross validated accuracy score for training set
print('Training accuracy Score: {:.5}'.format(tuned_mean_cv))
# uniform accuracy score for testing set
print('Testing accuracy Score: {:.5}'.format(tuned_base_accuracy))

Training accuracy Score: 0.86033
Testing accuracy Score: 0.85636
```

Fig. 19: Testing and Training Accuracy

```
----- SVM Baseline with Count Vectorizer -----
              precision    recall  f1-score   support

class 0       0.29         0.50         0.36         427
class 1       0.95         0.88         0.91        5747
class 2       0.79         0.88         0.83        1261

accuracy                   0.86         0.86         0.86        7435
macro avg                 0.68         0.75         0.70        7435
weighted avg              0.89         0.86         0.87        7435
```

Fig. 20: SVM value Count Vectorizer

	label	avg_positive	avg_neutral	avg_negative	avg_compound
0	0	0.083718	0.612277	0.300497	-0.362559
1	1	0.097999	0.619415	0.282064	-0.334533
2	2	0.115855	0.807687	0.075022	0.069780

Fig. 21: Average Polarity Score for Sentiment Analysis

From Fig. 21, Positive, Negative, and Neutral scores represent the proportion of text that falls into these categories.

- Hate Speech tweets on average are 8% positive, 61% neutral, and 30% negative.
- Offensive tweets on average are 9% positive, 61% neutral, and 33% negative.
- Neither tweets on average are 11% positive, 7% neutral, and 6% negative.

```
from sklearn.metrics import classification_report, confusion_matrix, accuracy_score
y_train_pred=clf.predict(X_train_vectorized)

print(confusion_matrix(y_train,y_train_pred))
print(classification_report(y_train,y_train_pred))
print(accuracy_score(y_train, y_train_pred))

[[ 26  0  0  9]
 [ 0 695 28 429]
 [ 0  6 3190 101]
 [ 0  66 106 15201]]
              precision    recall  f1-score   support

Gibberish Undetectable      1.00      0.74      0.85         35
      Hate Speech           0.91      0.60      0.72        1152
No Hate and Offensive       0.96      0.97      0.96        3297
      Offensive Language     0.97      0.99      0.98       15373

accuracy                   0.96      0.96      0.96       19857
macro avg                  0.96      0.83      0.88       19857
weighted avg               0.96      0.96      0.96       19857

0.9624817444729818
```

Fig. 22: Training accuracy of SVM

D. Testing

1) *Unit Testing*: Unit testing refers to the process of testing modules against the detailed design. The inputs to unit testing are the successfully compiled modules from the coding process. These are assembled during unit testing to make the largest units, i.e., the components of architectural design. Testing has been performed in each phase of project design and coding. The module interface is tested to ensure that information flows properly into and out of the program unit under test. The local data structure is examined to ensure that the data stored temporarily maintains its integrity throughout all steps of an algorithm's execution. And finally, all error-handling paths are tested.

2) *Integration Testing*: Integration testing is the phase in software testing in which individual software modules are combined and tested as a group. Integration testing is a level of software testing where individual units are combined and tested as a group. The purpose of this level of testing is to expose faults in the interaction between integrated units. Test drivers and test stubs are used to assist in integration testing.

Integration testing is conducted to evaluate a system or component's compliance with specified functional requirements. It occurs after unit testing and before validation testing.

Integration testing takes as input modules that have been unit-tested, groups them into larger aggregates, applies tests defined in an integration test plan to those aggregates, and delivers as output the integrated system ready for system testing.

3) *System Testing*: System testing is conducted on a complete, integrated system to evaluate its compliance with its specified requirements. System testing takes as input all integrated components that have passed integration testing. The purpose of integration testing is to detect inconsistencies between integrated units. System testing is concerned with identifying errors arising from unanticipated interactions between subsystems and system components. Once source code has been generated, software must be tested to uncover (and correct) as many errors as possible before delivery to customers. Our goal is to design a series of test cases that are highly likely to find errors.

System testing seeks to detect defects within the "inter-assemblages" and the system as a whole. The actual result is the behavior produced or observed when a component or system is tested. System testing is performed on the entire system in the context of functional requirement specifications (FRS), system requirement specifications (SRS), or both. System testing tests not only the design but also the behavior and even the customer's expectations.

E. Model Testing

Testing for Support Vector Machine

Case		Process	Result
Category	Actual		Predicted (Tuned Result)
Hate	0.61	Using Support Vector Machine	0.5
Offensive	0.91	Balanced the dataset using SMOTE+TOMEK link	0.88
Neither	0.95		0.88

Table II: Testing for Support Vector Machine

XII. CONCLUSION

Cyberbullying has far-reaching effects on its victims and should thus be prevented or seriously controlled. It subjects people to emotional torture to the extent that they begin to doubt their worth and value as human beings. Individuals may find it difficult to socialize with others, resorting to isolation or even physical self-harm. They may also adopt harmful lifestyles to alter their appearance. Preventing this detrimental phenomenon largely depends on the efforts of parents and schools.

This project focuses on the text-based cyberbullying detection problem, where robust, discriminative message representations are critical for an effective detection system. The proposed system aims to detect cyberbullying activity in social networks and categorize the text into hate speech, offensive language, or neither.

XIII. LIMITATION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

A. Limitation

- This system accepts text input only and does not detect images, videos, etc.
- There are various types of cyberbullying; this system is focused on the harassment category, specifically hate speech and offensive language.
- This system only detects grammatically correct English words.

B. Future Enhancement

- An automated AI system can be developed to better understand and detect offensive, hateful, and degrading human behavior.
- Online monitoring tools for parents, based on artificial intelligence, can be developed to provide better oversight of children's online activities.
- Detection of harassment and bullying in gaming platforms, which have recently seen increased incidents, would be effective and advantageous.

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APPENDICES

Fig. 23: Result 1 showing a category of Cyberbullying, i.e., No hate and offensive

Fig. 24: Result 2 showing a category of Cyberbullying, i.e., No hate and offensive